

Master in Sound and Music Computing
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Deploying the Groove Transformer to an Embedded Environment

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Abstract

Machine Learning (ML) models have proven to be an effective method for music generation. However, the level of control and interaction a user has with these models is often lacking in comparison to more traditional music tools. The complexity of these models continues to increase, however it appears to be at the expense of user agency over the models. Generative models have advanced far enough that they can dominate the creative and compositional process without the necessity of user input and interaction. Additionally, many of these models are primarily research-focused and therefore not deployed in frameworks that are conducive to a musician's performance or production workflow. In this thesis, we present an embedded generative neural network in the Eurorack format. The model known as the Groove Transformer is a Variational Auto-Encoder (VAE) that generates multi-channel drum patterns with micro-timing and velocity information. This model was previously deployed as a Pure-Data patch and VST plug-in intended for real-time drum accompaniment. Our adaptation, however, is the first dedicated physical interface for this generative model and among the first ML-based rhythm generators for Eurorack. The Groove Transformer module demonstrates that prioritizing user-control and model integration into existing workflows has potential to bring forth new affordances of a model and a level of customization and experimentation not present in other deployment frameworks.

Keywords: Rhythm generation; Eurorack; Generative neural network; Music interface; Musical expression

Chapter 1

Introduction

This Introduction will establish the backdrop for our study. We will begin by introducing the concept of modular synthesis in Section 1.1, focusing on early modular sequencers, specifically those in the Buchla Series 100. We then provide a concise recent history of algorithmic composition and describe its impact on musical creativity in Section 1.2. Our attention then shifts in Section 1.3 and Section 1.4 as we examine the application of Machine Learning (ML) in music, common deployment methods, and user interaction. Finally, in Section 1.5 we delve into the motivations behind this study: the adaptation of a software plug-in drum generator to a hardware Eurorack sequencer and the continued development of an emerging intelligent sequencer design paradigm.

1.1 Early Modular Synthesizers

During the mid-20th century, modular synthesizers, pioneered by influential figures such as Don Buchla and Robert Moog, represented a historic shift in sound generation and music composition. Unlike traditional synthesizers with fixed signal paths that would follow years later, a modular synthesizer is comprised of a collection of individual modules—each dedicated to a specific sonic function—interconnected through patch cables. This modularity enabled artists to assemble custom signal chains and explore an array of sonic possibilities. Figure 1 shows Don Buchla’s first

modular system, the Buchla Series 100¹. A fundamental tool included in the Buchla Series 100 was one of the first analog sequencers, a musical device that generates evolving patterns of control voltages or gate signals to generate notes or control other parameters in the system. American composer and Buchla collaborator Morton Subotnick had this to say about his use of the Buchla Series 100 sequencers:

There were three voltage-controlled outputs for each stage. I used to cascade two sequencers so that they would run simultaneously, giving you six voltages per stage. One voltage would control pitch, another spatial location, the third amplitude. Then one, which was really clever, would control the pulse generator that was controlling the sequencer, so that you could determine the absolute rhythm. You could literally program a very complex rhythm over a long period of time, for example, by running five stages against 13. [1]

Subotnick’s approach to composing music on the Buchla Series 100 alludes to another concept that continued to emerge around that time—algorithmic composition.

1.2 Algorithmic Composition

Algorithmic Composition can be described as “the process of using some formal process to make music with minimal human intervention” [2]. While today we normally associate this process with computers, early examples accomplish this task with the aid of various formalisms, such as random number generation, rule-based systems, and other types of algorithms [2]. The first instance of a computer generated music composition is attributed to Lejaren Hiller with the help of Leonard Isaacson and Robert Baker at the University of Illinois in 1955-56 [2]. Using the high-speed Illiac computer, Hiller and Isaacson attempted to simulate the compositional process by using a generator/modifier/selector approach. More specifically, the process generates “raw material” as a base, applies various techniques to it such as permutations

¹https://electricmusicbox.com/?page_id=157

Figure 1: Buchla Series 100

and geometric transformations, and, finally, applies rules in order to select suitable material for a composition to be performed on traditional instruments [2]. By 1963, early computer music pioneer Iannis Xenakis developed a program that creates “stochastic music” as detailed in his book *Formalized Music* [3]. The purpose of the program was to employ “interlinked probability functions to determine the global structure (e.g. length of sections) and the note parameters (e.g. pitch, duration) of a composition” [4]. This approach is similar to earlier aleatoric music (compositions that are subjected to structured randomness), but Xenakis’s algorithmic generations employed a much stricter mathematical basis that would pave the way for more advanced models later on. In the contemporary landscape, algorithmic composition has evolved to include computer software that is capable of generating endless variations of a musical piece as well as AI-driven systems that learn from existing musical data. Today, the convergence of modular synthesizers and algorithmic composition represents a new frontier of sonic exploration and artistic innovation.

1.3 The State of Machine Learning and Music

A recent literature review gives a useful overview of the application of Machine Learning (ML) at the New Interfaces for Musical Expression (NIME) conference over the past 10 years [5]. In an attempt to contextualize our own ML project, we are primarily concerned with three aspects of the study: the percentage of projects that allow for user-controlled model parameters, the percentage of projects in which users are included in the design and evaluation process, and for which type of applications ML is used. Of the 69 relevant NIME papers that were reviewed, 19 percent are for music information retrieval tools, 16 percent are related to artificial creativity (generative models), and 65 percent are used for human-machine improvisation (generative models that adapt to real-time data) [5]. Figures 2, 3, and 4 display the remaining results and mark which classification fits our proposal. The results reveal that only 30 percent of the applications in the study allow for user control over model parameters and only 27 percent allow for user control over training data. In looking at user involvement in the design process, it was found that 15 percent include users at the beginning of the process, 13 percent include users in the middle, and 29 percent include users at the end as part of an evaluation process. 43 percent do not include users at all in the design, conception, or evaluation process. [5].

Figure 2: Percent Breakdown of Applications that Allow User Control over Model Parameters

Figure 3: Percent Breakdown of Applications that Allow User Control over Training Data

Figure 4: Percent Breakdown of When Users are Included in Design Process

The findings from these analyses show that while the majority of applications are intended for human-machine improvisation, only a minority of these allow users to exert control over the model or training data. The study attempts to explain this finding by highlighting how the utilization of deep learning has facilitated complex creative interactions while simultaneously diminishing user agency. There is a prevalence of models geared towards automated processing, with limited user access to the underlying model formation process [5]. This observation serves as a pivotal motivation for our research. In contrast to perpetuating the trajectory of entirely automated generative models, our focus lies on the development of real-time performance-centric music generation systems characterized by a high degree of user interaction and parameter control. However, this aspiration necessitates careful consideration of the interface and ML deployment framework.

1.4 Control, Interaction, and Deployment Frameworks

While ML models have proven to be remarkably effective as music generation tools, the methods in which they are deployed are often uncondusive to a musician’s creative workflow. Deploying these models in a format that is accessible and useful to an artist is oftentimes costly for researchers and may surpass their area of expertise. As a result, researchers commonly resort to deploying their models through more streamlined and efficient means.

Two common approaches for allowing access to ML models are to provide a unique API for use through the command-line or to use a cloud-based interactive computing platform like Google Colab [6]. While these deployment methods offer some level of interaction with the model, they are not without substantial limitations. Specifically, these methods demand users to possess a certain level of technical proficiency within the chosen framework. Even if this criterion is met, neither of these methods provide a user-interface optimized for music production or performance contexts.

Instead of a command-line tool or cloud-based platform, researchers may use an interactive website to host a model as is the case with folk-rnn [7], MuseNet [8], Latent Space Exploration [9] and Magenta.js [10]. Interactive websites present a notable advancement compared to command-line tools or cloud-based platforms, as they generally eliminate the need for specialized technical expertise by offering a user-friendly and accessible interface. Despite this improvement, interactive websites still face challenges in seamlessly integrating into typical performance or production workflows.

Perhaps one of the best ways to integrate a ML-model into a music workflow is to develop a standalone application or plug-in to be hosted in a production environment such as a Digital Audio Workstation (DAW), MaxMSP², or PureData³. This method not only provides a dedicated interface for interacting with the model, but it also

²<https://cycling74.com/products/max>

³<https://puredata.info/>

facilitates easy integration with other music making tools that are commonly used for music production or performance.

1.5 Motivations

In this study, we are specifically focused on adapting a previously developed generative drum model called Groove Transformer to the Eurorack format. This model, trained with hours of live drum recordings [11], is a 9-channel symbolic drum generator that is capable of serving as a live accompaniment to a performing musician. Rather than merely cloning the existing system into a hardware format, we looked to re-conceptualize its design by deploying the model to a more flexible format and implementing an intelligent interface abstraction (see Section 1.5.2).

1.5.1 Adapting an Existing Generative Model to Eurorack

In recent years, the research of the Music and Multimodal Interaction (MMI) Lab has been predominantly focused on the advancement of real-time, performance-oriented deep generative systems for symbolic music [12]. The principal aim has been to design and build lightweight systems capable of being deployed as software plugins so as to allow for a practical user interface with state-of-the-art generative models.

While deploying a symbolic generative system like Groove Transformer as a MIDI plugin brings convenience and ease of use, it also harbors certain inherent limitations that need to be highlighted. Such plugins, specifically designed for integration within a DAW environment, may have rigid control sets and functionalities. As a result, users can often be easily confined within a defined application scope that aligns with the intended use of the plugin. For instance, in the case of the Groove Transformer VST plug-in for Ableton Live⁴, a user only has to add the plug-in to a MIDI track with a drum kit. The architecture of the plug-in integration with the DAW will automatically assign each channel of the plug-in to the corresponding drum hit on the MIDI track (for example, the kick drum output of the plug-in will trigger the kick drum in the Ableton drum kit) and it will automatically assign each channel's

⁴<https://www.ableton.com/en/>

velocity output to the velocity control on the MIDI track. This is excellent for ease of use and for encouraging the original use case of the model, which is to mimic a live, human-sounding drum performance. However, this does not encourage or, in some ways, does not allow the user to control the model and manipulate the outputs in ways not originally intended. For example, in the case of the Groove Transformer model, the velocity and micro-timing dynamics of a drum pattern could be repurposed to control other musical parameters or to influence entirely different aspects of a composition.

In this work, our aim is to challenge this conventional use and inspire a more expansive and explorative approach to these generative models. Rather than adhering strictly to the originally intended application of the Groove Transformer model, we wanted to develop a deployment strategy in which the users are forced to define the musical semantics associated with the generated patterns. By re-imagining these musical attributes, users can extend the functionality of the generative systems beyond the originally imposed boundaries. This new perspective invites users to engage with these generative models in a broader, more creative context than what was originally envisioned.

In order to encourage this explorative approach to the application of deep generative models, we have identified the Eurorack modular synthesizer format as an effective deployment environment. The Eurorack format, known for its flexibility and openness to creative patching, presents an ideal environment for the kind of user-model dialogue we aimed to foster. Thriving on the principle of modularity, the Eurorack format offers a high degree of customization and control over the signal flow. In this format, every module in the system, every patched connection between modules, and every interaction is determined by the user. This leads to uniquely curated systems for a wide array of uses. In an adaptation of the Groove Transformer plug-in to Eurorack, all aspects of the generated patterns could be provided to the user as separate streams of control voltages. In return, the user is responsible for routing the generated voltage streams according to their system and compositional goals. Essentially, the user is forced to redefine and re-purpose the musical semantics

associated with the generated patterns.

These fundamental concepts of modular sequencers have been defined since the inception of the format. However, with the recent surge in popularity of the Eurorack format, an influx of diverse sequencer designs have emerged.

1.5.2 Eurorack Sequencer Interfaces

In "Latent Drummer" [13], the authors provide an insightful analysis that claims new sequencer designs have primarily focused on introducing layers of abstraction to relinquish user control over the minutiae of musical decision making. They identify two key types of interface abstractions prevalent in modular sequencers: deterministic abstraction and stochastic abstraction.

The deterministic abstraction showcases a sequencer's capacity to alter the length and rhythm of steps through straightforward rules. These rules create mappings to rhythms that emphasize meter and syncopation while minimizing individual note control [13]. The Intellijel Metropolis⁵ is an 8-stage sequencer that is capable of complex sequences simply through high level rules that control sequence length, pulses per stage, and sequence order. Another example of deterministic abstraction widely adopted in Eurorack sequencers is the Euclidean rhythm, characterized by the simple rule of evenly distributing a specified number of notes across a defined set of steps [14].

The stochastic approach to interface abstraction involves the incorporation of probability controls into the design of the sequencer. This often materializes as per-step probability controls governing specific parameters like pitch, note length, or note divisions. An example of this would be the per-step probability controls of the Malekko Varigate 8+⁶.

While deterministic interface abstractions and stochastic interface abstractions have played a crucial role in enhancing the capabilities of modular sequencers, our project,

⁵<https://intellijel.com/shop/eurorack/metropolis/>

⁶<https://malekkoheavyindustry.com/product/varigate-8/>

like the Latent Drummer, is aiming to develop an emerging third type— intelligent interface abstraction. As it relates to our purposes, this new type of interface makes use of an intelligent model in order to abstract away elements of the compositional process that may hinder the necessary immediacy of a live performance. More specifically, our adaptation allows a user in a performance setting to improvise upon a multi-channel drum sequence with per-note micro-timings and velocity. The culmination of this work is an open-source hardware prototype (shown in Figure 5) that prioritizes user control over the generative process and flexibility in the application of the model’s outputs.

In the next chapter, we will discuss other work that we found to be inspirational or relevant to our project. In Chapter 3 we will dive into our design and adaptation process, highlighting how we use intelligent abstraction to merge the capabilities of deep generative models and conventional sequencer design paradigms for new forms of musical expression. Then, in Chapter 4 we will discuss the results and initial observations of our prototype. Finally, in Chapter 5, we offer some conclusions and potential areas for future work.

Figure 5: The final developed module

Chapter 2

Related Work

For over a decade, the increasing accessibility of Machine Learning (ML) tools has influenced the development of new musical instruments, an early example being Rebecca Fiebrink’s Wekinator, which enables users to easily train their own neural networks to interpret any number of inputs [15]. More recently, the accessibility of software libraries like TensorFlow⁷, Keras⁸, and PyTorch⁹ has encouraged even further development of intelligent music systems and interfaces. In this chapter, we will examine some recent examples of intelligent musical interfaces that we find most relevant to our work. First, we will discuss AI-terity, a deformable musical instrument which showcases an advanced intelligent interface abstraction coupled with a real-time generative model. We will then introduce a generative drum model that utilizes the concept of a rhythm space for pattern generation. Lastly, we will explore three Eurorack modules that leverage ML models, the Mutable Instruments Grids, IRCAM’s Neurorack module, and the Latent Drummer module.

AI-terity is a deformable, non-rigid musical instrument that implements an AI model for generating audio samples for real-time audio synthesis [16]. The instrument employs a Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) to translate a user’s tactile interactions with a tangible object into the parameters of a granular synthesizer. This

⁷<https://www.tensorflow.org/>

⁸<https://keras.io/>

⁹<https://pytorch.org/>

approach allows users to exert physical force on the interface, as if they are shaping and manipulating sound itself through their actions. Underneath the interface, the model is leveraging Principal Component Analysis (PCA) in order to let the user navigate the latent space in a non-random meaningful way. Although this instrument is an audio generator rather than a sequencer, its interface adheres to the concept of an intelligent interface abstraction that was introduced earlier. Rather than a user having to meticulously adjust or automate each parameter of this granular engine, the parameters are abstracted away from the user in favor of a tactile interface that uses an intelligent model to create intuitive interactions and control.

In [17], Gómez-Marín et. al. explore how the perception of rhythm can be leveraged in interactions with compositional tools such as a drum generation model. Citing the importance of rhythm similarity in perceiving drum patterns, this study carries out two experiments exploring human processing of polyphonic drum patterns. These experiments result in a list of descriptors that significantly influence similarity sensations. The descriptors are then used by a software system to build rhythm spaces based on drum pattern collections. In the resulting spaces, patterns are organized by similarity and modeled according to human ratings. As is the case with AI-terity, this application abstracts away the fine grained controls of the music generation process, in this case drum pattern generation, and instead implements an intelligent system in an effort to develop an intuitive control interface.

The Mutable Instruments Grids is a 3-channel trigger generator for Eurorack designed to create and shape rhythmic patterns [18]. At the core of Grids is a 2-dimensional map, generated through machine learning techniques, that encapsulates drum patterns extracted from an extensive collection of electronic music tracks and drum loops. By selecting X and Y coordinates on this map, users can establish a symbolic drum pattern, which can then be smoothly interpolated between points to generate variations. Notably, the density of each channel's events can be controlled, enabling transitions from sparse foundations to more intricate patterns. The ability to manipulate X/Y map positions and channel densities via control voltage (CV) modulation offers a versatile approach to crafting rhythmic diversity. While the 3

channels on Grids are typically associated with a kick drum, snare drum, and hi-hat, it encourages experimentation with different sound sources.

IRCAM’s Neurorack was the first real-time generative model in the Eurorack format [19]. This model generates audio in the form of impact sounds from the distribution of 7 adjustable descriptors (Loudness, Percussivity, Noisiness, Tone-like, Richness, Brightness, Pitch). Additionally, the model allows for a second impact with separate descriptor values to be merged with the main impact. A CV-controlled parameter allows a user to interpolate between these two generated impacts for a hybrid sound. It should be noted that a main component of this model is that it is lightweight computationally and in memory footprint. This allows the model to be embedded in a single NVIDIA Jetson Nano¹⁰ board.

The Latent Drummer [13] is another recent example of a generative model intended for Eurorack. Unlike the Neurorack module which is an audio generation model, the Latent Drummer is a symbolic score generation model. The foundation of [13] is a classic 16-step drum sequencer with five channels. However, to expand upon that, the system utilizes a Variational Autoencoder (VAE) to generate drumming styles and a set of Markov Models to improvise within the generated style [13]. The VAE was trained to encode simple drawings created on a Roli Lightpad¹¹ board, which is included on the module interface, into an 8-dimensional latent space. Using this light pad and a set of knobs, a user can guide pattern generation, improvisation amount, and the overall density of each channel’s output. As of the most recent publication, this prototype runs on a laptop and interfaces with Eurorack through a PolyEnd Poly2¹² MIDI to CV module.

¹⁰<https://developer.nvidia.com/embedded/jetson-nano-developer-kit>

¹¹<https://roli.com/products/blocks/lightpad-block-studio-edition>

¹²https://polyend.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/Polyend_Poly2_Manual_web2.pdf

Chapter 3

Methodology

This section will outline the evolution of the Groove Transformer model into the Groove Transformer Eurorack module. First, in Section 3.1 we will introduce the architecture of the original model and provide a high-level overview of how it works. Then, in Section 3.2 we will discuss the new affordances brought on by our adaptation of the model to the Eurorack format. In Section 3.3, we explain the front panel design process of the Groove Transformer module. Lastly, in Section 3.4 and Section 3.5, we will describe the hardware design and software design of the Groove Transformer module.

3.1 Existing Groove Transformer Accompaniment System

The underlying generative model of the Groove Transformer module for Eurorack is a Variational Auto-Encoder (VAE). This VAE model accepts a single channel input of a 32-step sequence with per-step micro-timings and velocity. This input, referred to as the *input groove* is encoded into a latent space and subsequently decoded into 32-step 9-channel drum pattern with per-step micro-timings and velocity. This architecture of the VAE model is shown in Figure 6. The VST plug-in deployment of this system leveraged the VAE model as a real-time drum accompaniment tool.

Figure 6: Generative Model

A musician performing live on a MIDI instrument could use the notes they were playing as the input groove. This input groove would condition the model to generate rhythmically similar patterns that could be used for drum accompaniment. The intended application for this was to generate realistic, human-like drum patterns by using the model outputs to trigger the sounds of a traditional drum kit. While these early applications were very effective for realistic drum-accompaniment, they did have some limitations. Due to the architecture and DAW integration of the plug-in, assigning the outputs to playback or trigger anything other than synthesized notes or samples in a DAW would be very challenging or impossible. For example, the plug-in does not allow a user to assign a channel to trigger envelopes or to reset a low frequency oscillator (LFO) that modulates/automates some other parameter. Assigning the model's output velocity value to control a parameter other than velocity may also prove difficult or impossible in the plug-in version of the model. Lastly, the plug-in version *required* an input groove in order to generate a pattern.

3.2 Adaptation for Eurorack

While real-time interaction is still important in a Eurorack environment, the emphasis tends to be less on tight coordination with a live performer. Instead, the focus is on using intricate sequences, complex waveforms, and a variety of control voltage in order to explore the wide range of sonic possibilities with a system. Frequently, users may automate or inject randomness into these processes and allow for autonomous and complex behavior to develop.

Contrast this with a real-time drum accompaniment system that is designed to respond dynamically to a live input. While the capabilities of the Groove Transformer model as a real-time drum accompaniment tool can still be useful in a Eurorack system, the inherent difference in interaction modality and purpose between these two systems requires rethinking and redefining how to best leverage a generative system in a Eurorack environment. In the case of the Groove Transformer, we identified the latent space of the VAE model as an opportunity to expand the system’s capabilities past the original use case. More specifically, we added controls that allow the performer to navigate the latent space, recall points in the latent space, and allow for both conditioned and *unconditioned* pattern generation. The creative and performative potential of a system like this becomes especially clear when you pair it with the inherent customizability of a Eurorack system and the high level of user control over signal flow and parameter changes.

3.2.1 Latent Space Interpolation Control

To facilitate the construction and navigation of the latent space, the interface allows a performer to save 2 separate latent vector values as State A and State B which are represented by points Z_A and Z_B in Figure 7. The interpolation parameter α shown on the figure is the interpolation of the latent vector between these points Z_A and Z_B . This parameter allows for a performer to “improvise” and maintain a degree of rhythmic similarity between two known patterns Z_A and Z_B . If the interpolation parameter α is placed under CV control, the result is as if the model

itself is leading the improvisation. To further expand on this new affordance to the model, a third point, Z_{Groove} , can be placed in the latent space. When one is present, this point represents the input groove and allows for bilinear interpolation. Because the position Z_{Groove} changes as the input groove changes, these three points represent a dynamic boundary of the interpolation area within the latent space. In Figure 7, the interpolation value between Z_{AB} and Z_{Groove} is represented by β and determines how closely the system is following the input groove. When this value is at its maximum ($Z_{ABG} = Z_{Groove}$), the system acts fully as a drum accompaniment to the input groove. When it's at its minimum value, the output of the system acts independent of the input groove and the output will directly correspond to the value of α . Therefore, this parameter allows for dynamic performances by acting as a control for the overall autonomy of the system.

Figure 7: Latent Space Bilinear Interpolation

3.3 Panel Design and Controls

The design of the main interface panel involved two main steps: defining the parameters to be incorporated and arranging them logically on the interface. To initiate this process, we first examined the parameters present in the initial Groove Transformer VST plug-in. We retained parameters essential for the core functionality of the model or those that offered valuable control over its operations. Furthermore, certain parameters not explicitly present on the VST plug-in interface needed to be included on the Eurorack interface. This refers primarily to parameters related

to clock or external interfacing (control voltage, MIDI) which are typically handled within the DAW hosting the plug-in. Lastly, it was necessary to ensure that our chosen hardware (discussed in Section 3.4) could accommodate all of the desired parameters.

Table 1 identifies and lists each interface component and classifies them into five distinct categories: *Utility Parameters*, *CV/MIDI Pattern Generation Output*, *Input Groove Controls*, *Generation Controls*, and *Latent Space Interpolation Controls*. *Utility Parameters* are the parameters necessary to operate the system but that do not affect the pattern generations. This includes tempo control parameters, controls to start and stop the system, and record/overdub control. *CV/MIDI Pattern Generation Outputs* are the note sequences and velocities generated by the model. These CV and MIDI outputs are control signals intended for other modules or hardware. *Input Groove Controls* affect the input groove used to condition the system's outputs for use as a real-time drum accompaniment. This includes parameters that quantize the velocities of the input groove's notes and their locations on the grid. *Generation Controls* are those parameters that affect the sampling parameters of the model or apply post-processing to the generated patterns. These parameters include Uncertainty, Voice Density, and Voice Velocity Scale. Finally, *Latent Space Interpolation Controls* are the parameters described in the previous section that affect the arrangement and navigation of the latent space.

The panel design process involved a methodical approach to arranging the parameters and components in a coherent and usable way. Drawing inspiration from existing Eurorack modules, we aimed to align with common design patterns found within the Eurorack format. We began with low-fidelity sketches, shown in Figure 8, and then progressed to high-fidelity software designs (Figure 9) using Synth Panels Designer¹³, which is an Inkscape¹⁴ plug-in. The choice of fabrication material played a crucial role in the overall look and feel of our module. Our initial attempt was a laser-cut wood panel. The result was satisfactory, but we thought an alternative material may offer a cleaner and sturdier panel. This led us to experiment with a

¹³<https://www.synthpanels.design/>

¹⁴<https://inkscape.org/>

Table 1: Interface Components

	Index	Name	Description
Utility Parameters	1	Internal Clock Tempo Knob	Sets the internal clock tempo
	2	Internal Clock CV Output	CV clock output
	3	External Clock CV Input	Input for external CV clock source
	4	Metronome Click Output	Metronome click audio output
	5	Play/Stop Switch	Starts and stops the outputs and input groove record buffer
	6	Record/Overdub/Off Switch	Three-way switch to change the mode of the input groove record buffer
	7	Clear Button	Clears the input groove record buffer
	8	Shift Button	Enables secondary functions of other buttons
CV/MIDI Pattern Generation Output	9	CV Gate Voice Output	MIDI output and CV gate and velocity output for each voice
	10	CV Velocity Voice Output	
	11	MIDI Output	
Input Groove Control	12	Input Groove CV Gate Input	MIDI input and CV gate and velocity input for input groove
	13	Input Groove CV Velocity Input	
	14	Input Groove MIDI Input	
	15	Input Groove Velocity Knob	Quantizes the input groove to the grid and quantizes the velocity of each note
	16	Input Groove Offset Knob	
Generation Control	17	Uncertainty Knob	Sets the value of the Uncertainty parameter
	18	Uncertainty CV Input	CV input for the Uncertainty parameter
	19	Voice Density Knob	Controls the number of hits in each sequence by adjusting the threshold of the model
	20	Voice Velocity Scale Knob	Scales the velocity output. At minimum value, no scaling is applied to the outputs. At maximum value, all velocities are scaled to the maximum value.
Latent Space Interpolation	21	Preset Selection Knob	Selects the preset number to be loaded or to be saved to. A preset consists of the saved states in the latent space Z_A and Z_B
	22	Preset Save/Load Button	Saves current states Z_A and Z_B to the selected preset number. Pressing with shift button loads the preset at the selected preset number
	23	Save/Randomize A and B Button	Sets the current state to be Z_A or Z_B in the latent space. Pressing with shift button generates a random placement for Z_A or Z_B in the latent space
	24	A/B Interpolation Slider	Interpolation position between states Z_A and Z_B in the latent space
	25	A/B Interpolation CV Input	CV input to automate the interpolation position in the latent space
	26	A/B Interpolation CV Knob	Attenuates the A/B Interpolation CV input in the latent space
	27	Follow Knob	Sets the value of the Follow parameter in the latent space
	28	Follow CV Input	CV input to automate the Follow parameter

methacrylate sheet which improved the sturdiness of the panel and resulted in much cleaner laser cut holes for components. To complete the panel's aesthetics, we opted to print a sticker of the interface labels and artwork. The culmination of this design process is depicted in Figure 10.

Figure 8: Early Panel Design Sketches

Figure 9: Software Panel Designs

3.4 Hardware Design

The Groove Transformer implements a dual-board approach using both an Electro-Smith Daisy Seed¹⁵ microcontroller and a Libre AML-S905X-CC¹⁶ single board computer. The Daisy Seed board is a microcontroller platform specifically designed for audio programming and instrument creation. The Daisy Seed handles CV and MIDI inputs on the module interface, manages MIDI and CV playback of the patterns, and serves as the master clock. The AML-S905X-CC is used to perform real-time inference. These two boards communicate via a two-way UART connection. Parameter control values are transmitted from the interface (Daisy Seed) and received by the model (AML-S905X-CC). As the model receives new input grooves and/or parameter control values, it transmits newly generated patterns to the module interface.

¹⁵<https://www.electro-smith.com/daisy/daisy>

¹⁶<https://libre.computer/products/aml-s905x-cc/>

Figure 10: Final Software Panel Designs

This communication architecture is illustrated in Figure 11. Although it's possible that we could have used a single board approach for this project, our primary objective was to have a working hardware prototype for the Eurorack adaptation of the model. We did not prioritize optimizing the size of the model for an embedded environment.

In order to expand the capabilities of the Daisy Seed board we used two other key components, an Adafruit MCP4728 Quad Digital to Analog Converter (DAC)¹⁷ and a CD4051 Multiplexer¹⁸. By utilizing a single I2C connection on the Daisy Seed board, we were able to implement 2 Quad DACs allowing for 8 additional analog outputs on the interface. These were assigned to the output pattern's gate and velocity CV. The CD4051 Multiplexer, however, was used to expand the number of possible inputs. With this multiplexer, we are able to expand the input of a single Analog to Digital Converter (ADC) pin on the Daisy Seed into 8 separate inputs. These multiplexers were essential in allowing us to accommodate the number of controllable parameters and CV inputs we have on the interface.

The final essential hardware component is the PCB, which serves as the host for

¹⁷<https://www.adafruit.com/product/4470>

¹⁸<https://www.ti.com/lit/ds/symlink/cd4051b.pdf>

Figure 11: Hardware Communication

the previously mentioned boards and components. To ensure reliability and address spatial limitations, a dual PCB board design was adopted. This arrangement effectively allocates space for all interface components on the top board (shown in Figure 12), while accommodating the boards, DACs, multiplexers, and other elements on the bottom board (shown in Figure 13). The increased space also facilitates the integration of a patch bay for the pins on the Daisy Seed board. Although manual soldering was required for every connection between a Daisy Seed pin and a component, this patch bay design provided the desired flexibility to reassign or remove any connections in the event of a faulty PCB or unforeseen design change. PCB designs were created using EasyEDA Design Software¹⁹ and then manufactured by JLCPCB²⁰.

3.5 Software Design

The software design was structured to ensure effective collaboration between the module interface and the model. The programming language on the Daisy Seed is

¹⁹<https://easyeda.com/>

²⁰<https://jlcpcb.com/>

Figure 12: Top PCB - Software Design and Manufactured Board

Figure 13: Bottom PCB - Software Design and Manufactured Board

C++ and makes use of the LibDaisy and DaisySP libraries. These libraries provide support for common audio tasks and signal processing tasks. On the Libre AML-S905X-CC board is the Pytorch model. As elaborated in the Hardware Design section (Section 3.4), communication between these boards occurs through encoded UART messages, with Daisy Seed sending parameter changes from the module interface and Libre AML-S905X-CC sending generated patterns from the model. These architectures are illustrated in Figure 14 and Figure 15. When Daisy Seed receives messages, they are decoded and properly directed to the playback manager for MIDI and CV playback control. When the Libre AML-S905X-CC receives messages they are decoded and directed either to the Input Groove Manager or the Latent Space Manager, both of which ultimately update the model and influence generated patterns. This software framework ensures that the boards remain in sync and that patterns can be played and generated without interruption. The complete code can be found on the GitHub repositories for this project²¹²².

²¹<https://github.com/evans398/DaisyGrooveTransformer>

²²<https://github.com/evans398/GrooveTransformerPi>

Figure 14: Daisy Seed Communication Architecture

Figure 15: Libre AML-S905X-CC Communication Architecture

3.6 Assembly Process

The main step in assembling the module was soldering each component to the PCBs. This included making the manual "patch bay" solder connections to each pin of the Daisy Seed as was discussed in Section 3.4. Fortunately, we encountered no issues with the design or manufacturing of the PCBs. We verified that the Daisy Seed is accurately reading values from the interface components and also outputting the correct values to the CV and MIDI outputs. UART communication between the boards is also functioning properly. Parameter values from the interface are successfully transmitted by Daisy Seed and received by the Libre AML-S905X-CC. Pattern generations are successfully transmitted by the Libre AML-S905X-CC and received by Daisy Seed. The inference time of the embedded model is about 20ms. This is quick enough that we have not experienced any issues with delay or syncing.

Chapter 4

Results

At this time, there is a complete and functional prototype of the Groove Transformer module. However, a formal evaluation of the module has yet to be performed. In this section, however, we will present some preliminary findings and results of the project. First we will review the assembly process and some early observations about the module’s performance. Then, we will talk about two notable events in which we were able to showcase our work– Sónar Barcelona²³ and +RAIN Film Fest²⁴. Finally, we will discuss some potential improvements potential improvements that we have already identified.

4.1 Preliminary Testing

Although the module has not yet undergone formalized user testing, there are some initial observations that can be highlighted here. One promising result is that the latent space interpolation feature appears to be a powerful improvisational tool. The generated patterns morph in ways that keep the performance coherent rather than sounding random. One useful technique with this feature is to start with a preset loaded for State A and State B. Then, begin moving the slider towards State B. This will begin morphing the generated output until it starts to resemble the pattern at

²³<https://sonar.es/es>

²⁴<https://www.upf.edu/es/web/rainfilmfest/rain>

State B. When the slider is all the way at State B, either load a different preset to State A or randomize State A. Now you can move the slider back towards State A to continue generating new pattern variations without breaks in rhythmic continuity. When the slider is back to State A, a new preset or randomized latent vector can be loaded to State B to repeat the process. Using this method, a performer can generate endless pattern variations between known musical ideas (presets) or randomized states while preserving the fluidness and rhythmic continuity of the performance. Additionally, this technique can be especially useful when coupled with a slow LFO or long envelope to control slider position.

We have also made some observations while patching the the outputs of the module to the rest of the system. First, without making use of the velocity CV outputs of the Groove Transformer and only patching the trigger outputs to trigger 4 full-voice (oscillator, voltage controlled amplifier (VCA), and envelope generator (EG)) drum modules, we found that the results were non-expressive and unsatisfactory. This is likely the case because many of the patterns have low velocity hits meant to be accents or ghost notes. Triggering every hit at maximum velocity disrupts the groove of the pattern. Next, we decided to patch the audio from each drum voice into an additional VCA and patch the velocity outputs of the Groove Transformer to their corresponding drum voice and VCA. This patch effectively uses velocity for how it's typically thought of, amplitude control. In this case, even when our patched drum sounds were not analogous to those of a typical acoustic drum kit, the results were more expressive and musically useful enough for a live performance or recording. To expand a bit further on this patch, we decided to take multiples of the velocity signals and patch them to a parameter that is commonly found on most full-voice drum modules— decay. Since decay and amplitude are both related to the force in which a drum is struck, this patch does even more to mimic the physical response of a real drum even when we use non-traditional synthesized sounds.

After establishing these initial patches, we looked for alternative ways to patch the outputs of the Groove Transformer. Two specific drum modules we used that offer many voltage controlled parameters are the Noise Engineering Basimilus Iteritas

Alter²⁵ (BIA) and the ALM Akemie's Taiko²⁶. These modules use frequency modulation (FM) synthesis to produce novel percussive sounds and textures. Patching the Groove Transformer's velocity output to the BIA's wavefold or morph parameter or to Akemie's Taiko FM algorithm or FM ratio parameter, created interesting timbre changes and began to take us further from the original intended use case of "human-like" drums. In some cases, these sounds alternated between being very percussive and being more of a synthesized melody or texture. We found that using the velocity outputs to modulate timbral parameters sometimes starts to introduce a new expressive groove to the generated patterns that is not present when only patching velocity to amplitude. It is also worth noting that by using a multiple of the velocity signal, this timbral modulation can be integrated into the density and amplitude control patch mentioned previously.

The Groove Transformer's trigger outputs can also be used for creative patches. Instead of only using the Groove Transformer's velocity outputs for CV control, we patched a multiple of a trigger output and used it to trigger both a full-voice drum module and an envelope on the XAOC Devices Zadar²⁷. This highly customizable envelope from the Zadar is synced with our drum pattern can then be patched to any number of parameters in the system. For our patch, we experimented with modulating parameters of the Make Noise Mimeophone²⁸ delay and reverb module. Patching the Zadar envelope to the parameters delay 'color' and delay 'repeats' resulted in some interesting sounds and patterns, especially with low density generations from the Groove Transformer. While this is just a single example, this patching technique offers endless possibilities for timed modulation that is synchronized with the Groove Transformer generations.

There have been two occasions in which we have showcased the module and the capabilities of the model. At Sónar Barcelona, we had a booth for the Sónar+D²⁹ Eurorack section of the festival. Here we were able to display the prototype, show

²⁵<https://noiseengineering.us/products/basimilus-iteritas-alter?color=black>

²⁶<https://busycircuits.com/alm015/>

²⁷http://xaocdevices.com/manuals/xaoc_zadar_manual.pdf

²⁸<https://www.makenoisemusic.com/modules/mimeophon>

²⁹<https://sonar.es/es/programa/sonar-d>

live demonstrations, and receive feedback from other Eurorack manufacturers and festival attendees. At +RAIN Film Fest we had the opportunity to showcase the model by doing an actual live performance. In this performance, all of the percussive elements were generated by the model interfacing with a Eurorack system and a Volca Beats³⁰ drum machine. The patch for this performance used the velocity outputs of the Groove Transformer to control the amplitude for each drum voice as well as various timbral parameters. Additionally, by using the model to trigger both a Volca Beats drum machine and a Eurorack system, we were able to expand the range of sounds and bring in different elements from each source at different times. A photo of this performance can be seen in Figure 16.

Figure 16: +RAIN Performance

4.2 Early Changes and Potential Improvements

Initial testing of the latent space interpolation feature showed that while the A/B slider was in use, it was sending a significant number of values over a short period of time. In order to prevent these messages from overloading the model and the UART connection, we decided to quantize the values of the A/B slider and all other parameters so that they send less values per adjustment. While this alleviates the

³⁰https://www.korg.com/es/products/dj/volca_beats/

main issue, it does come at the expense of some resolution for each parameter. Therefore, we would like to implement a solution that preserves the full resolution of each component's value without overloading the system.

Another area that could be improved is the trigger and velocity output section on the Groove Transformer module. The Groove Transformer *model* generates a 9-channel pattern while the Groove Transformer *module* only outputs 4 channels of gate and velocity pairs. As a result, of the 9 channels output by the model, we only keep the ones associated with the kick drum, snare, hi-hat, and toms (grouping together low, mid, and high toms). However, we have noticed that this can result in some sparse pattern generations that likely occur when the unused channels (open hi-hat, crash, or ride cymbal) have a significant number of hits in the pattern. For example, if a generated pattern has no tom hits and it uses the ride cymbal in place of a hi-hat pattern, the pattern output on the module will only reflect the kick drum and snare hits. If this sparse pattern appears while interpolating within the latent space, there is an undesired break in continuity. A possible solution to this is to dynamically adjust which channels are selected based on the number of hits. Keeping with the same example, the Groove Transformer module would adjust so that it outputs the pattern associated with the ride cymbal rather than the hi-hat pattern with no hits.

Additionally, it should be noted that the Groove Transformer module was originally intended to support 6 gate and velocity output pairs rather than 4. Unfortunately, we discovered after assembly that only 2 Adafruit MCP4728 Quad DACs can be supported with a single I2C connection. Therefore, implementing 2 DACs instead of 3, as we intended, means the module can only support 4 gate and velocity output pairs (the MIDI output is unaffected and supports up to 9 channels). While this presents only a minor limitation, this hardware issue is something we plan to address in future versions of the module.

Finally, addressing the module's dimensions is imperative, given that the current PCB height of the prototype blocks the module from being mounted in a typical Eurorack case. Ergonomic enhancements are also needed for the second row and fifth rows of the density and velocity knobs that are spaced too closely together.

Chapter 5

Future Work and Conclusions

In this project, we have established a useful hardware adaptation for the Groove Transformer model. The module excels at improvisation and allowing a user control over a model while abstracting away the small details of drum programming that are not conducive to live programming. Additionally, this module strikes a useful balance between being a tool for live accompaniment or being a source of inspiration and exploration. The benefits of Eurorack’s flexibility have also shown through in this project. The capabilities of the model expand quite a bit with the allowance to patch the outputs of the sequencer to different sounds, effects, and parameters. Considering this, it follows that the module could be further developed to generate volt-per-octave signals and versatile control voltages, potentially serving as a comprehensive central sequencer for a modular synthesizer. Eurorack’s inherent flexibility, coupled with a machine learning-driven interface, offers the best opportunity to create novel, improvised live performances.

A topic of further research for this project could be lightweight fine-tuning. Fine-tuning a model is the process of tweaking a pre-trained model so that it accomplishes a specific task. For our case, we can take two approaches to fine-tuning our model: a data-oriented approach or a feedback-oriented approach. In each approach the objective is to fine-tune the pre-trained model to meet the needs of a specific user. For the data-oriented approach, this would entail fine-tuning the pre-trained model

with curated data provided by the user. Ideally this would be done with a simplified interface that abstracts away from the user the process of formatting and preparing data. Depending on the type of data, the model capabilities can be expanded in different ways. For example, if trained with performance data of varying time-intervals, the model may be able to learn both long-term and short-term generations. If successful, this could potentially improve the model’s ability to guide or follow a full performance by the user.

An example of a feedback-oriented approach is Reinforcement Learning (RL). Similar to Supervised Learning (SL), RL uses a mapping between input and output. However, when using SL to train a sequence prediction model, it is notoriously difficult to train models to learn certain properties and to have a coherent global structure [20]. The difference between these methods is that RL uses rewards and punishments as feedback to a model while SL’s feedback is simply the correct set of actions for the task. In [20], Jaque et. al. show that their pretrained models fine-tuned with RL produce varied compositions which are more melodic, harmonious, and interesting than those of the original Note RNN model. For our purposes, fine-tuning with RL would involve feedback from the user. This could entail the user providing feedback on generations as they occur or looking back on an entire performance and providing feedback on specific parts. This method of training has the potential to expand the capabilities of the model compared to the original learning method that focuses strictly on 2-bar phrases.

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